

Auto-summarization of Human Volumetric Videos

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ABSTRACT

The rapid expansion of immersive interaction and visualization has led to the emergence of volumetric videos. However, analyzing information within such content is still in its early stages, primarily because well-established techniques for 2D videos and 3D animations are not directly applicable. This challenge stems from the limited availability of open-source volumetric content and the inherent difficulties in capturing volumetric videos. These obstacles have resulted in a notable gap in the fields of summarization, retrieval, and streaming of volumetric videos. This paper delves into the summarization of human volumetric videos by employing traditional shape descriptors, and pseudo-labels. The primary goal is to discern specific key frames within the sequence that distinctly stand out from their neighbouring frames, which are further labeled with a textual description of pose information per frame and a semantic action annotation of the sequence. Furthermore, the extracted metadata could be used in future applications, to enable users to search through large collections of volumetric video data.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Computing methodologies** → *Information extraction.*

KEYWORDS

Volumetric video summarization; volumetric video retrieval; automatic rigging; action recognition

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1 INTRODUCTION

Understanding human actions is a well-established problem that requires deciphering gestures, actions, and overall semantics from various data modalities. This also involves summarizing, either by describing the actions textually or condensing the lengthy content

into concise representations. Recent progress in multi-view capture systems has led to a significant increase in human volumetric videos (VV) [10, 17]. However, the increase in data demands reliable search and retrieval tools that permit immersive artists to readily use the VV's. While there is a significant amount of work on retrieving 3D models from sketches and texts [6], little work has been done on VV retrieval. Due to the increase in usage and availability of VV's, there is an increase in demand to automatically annotate VV's with relevant information or metadata to aid in search and retrieval. This metadata can encapsulate multi-modal information that describes the keyframes, actions, and natural language textual descriptions of postures.

Extraction of information in natural language descriptions of actions from 2D videos is well investigated with the help of available standard benchmarks [8, 23]. These methods are not directly applicable to VV due to the loss of information when rendered to a 2D view, causing occlusions of body parts that lead to inaccurate action classification results on a sequence. Additionally, a 2D view alone is insufficient to understand the posture of a human. However, capturing and processing the VV's alone stands as a major challenge due to the closely constrained space, and with a large number of cameras for high fidelity reconstruction. Therefore, deformable parametric templates like SMPL are used to understand human actions and motions rather than actual clothed humans or 2D views [15].

Our volumetric video annotation pipeline is comprised of various components, including keyframing, human pose registration, bridging the relationship between pose parameters to natural language textual descriptions, and semantic action classification. Selecting a set of keyframes in a sequence helps in reducing the computational and memory overheads by avoiding processing or streaming the entire sequence. Furthermore, these frames are efficient in describing the action of the entire sequence by interpolating the motion between keyframes [7]. There has been a growing interest in annotating human action sequences based on predetermined rules [3, 13], fine granular natural language textual descriptions supplements in generating temporally consistent human postures and actions [27]. Despite promising studies on individual components, current fragmented breakthroughs can be used to design a complete annotation pipeline.

Given the aforementioned shortcomings, this paper introduces two novel contributions to the field of VV comprehension that perform both textual annotations and summarization of sequence. Firstly, it presents a VV sequence classification model using a transformer architecture for semantic classification [4], which operates

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on pre-trained per-frame pose embeddings [3]. For training the semantic classifier a human-annotated dataset called BABEL is used [19]. BABEL consists of a wide range of actions starting from simple actions like *walk*, *jump*, and *stand-up* to complex actions involving human-object interactions like *lift something* and *interact with/use object*. Secondly, this paper also introduces a metadata extraction pipeline designed to identify keyframes within a sequence, automatically rig these keyframes, annotate textual descriptions for each keyframe, enabling the retrieval of specific poses through natural language, and ultimately facilitating semantic annotation of the sequence from the classification model. Finally, the proposed annotation pipeline is demonstrated on a publicly available VV dataset [17].

2 RELATED WORK

This section first provides an overview of keyframing, starting from 2D videos to VV's. Finally, it discusses the complementary nature of human action recognition using natural language descriptions.

2.1 Keyframing

2D video summarization, also known as 2D video keyframing, is the process of selecting the distinct frames of a sequence without any loss of predominant information. Extraction of keyframes or segments is done based on the desired information representations, such as features, clustering, event-based, and trajectory-based [21]. Primarily in human action sequences, these representations are the keypoints that track the kinematic trajectory of limb positions over time. Applications of the keypoint clusters in lower dimensional space are twofold, complementing each other: segmenting actions temporally and recognizing the actions them, respectively. Segmenting a 3D shape sequence is more challenging than 2D videos due to the unorganized and complex nature of the data. Traditionally, the various shape descriptor from the literature use contours or boundaries that only consider superficial information [1], regions along with abstract information [12], and transform-based descriptors [11]. Transform-based descriptors like spherical harmonic descriptors are more robust in describing the variations in human poses due to the continuous representation and invariance towards rotations, translations, and scale [11].

2.2 Human pose-action semantic representation

Initial human action recognition works predominantly focus on recognizing actions from 2D videos. Some of the most accurate action recognition models are trained using graph convolution networks (GCN) [22] and transformers [28] on skeletal information. However, the skeletal information alone is insufficient to understand the context of actions in a sequence. Recent developments in language models are transferred towards human action recognition tasks, which adds meaningful context to the actions. Encoding natural language context to actions requires granular semantic representations of actions. Not only are these semantic granular descriptions useful for action recognition, but they are effectively applicable to various other problems like Temporal action segmentation, Temporally consistent Motion generation, and motion in-betweening. The semantic representations of human motions are the captions generated from skeletal information alone. Simple predefined geometric booleans

are used to describe the relationship between various joints depending on angles and distances from human annotators [18]. However, large language models require more fine granular descriptions to describe the posture of a human based on simple boolean rules that undermine the ambiguous nature of human posture. Posescripts further extend the simple boolean-based descriptions into a rule-based textual aggregation from natural language templates [3]. These descriptions are more reliable for disambiguating different postures of humans and supplement the pose retrieval tasks.

3 METHODOLOGY

This paper introduces the annotation pipeline algorithm to extract the metadata of a human VV sequence. First, the process of extracting keyframes in a VV sequence is presented followed by pose registration of a scan. Next, the action classifier using pose tokens from an encoder aligned with textual descriptions is presented. The overall annotation pipeline, given a VV sequence, is illustrated in Figure 1.

3.1 Keyframing

The spherical harmonics descriptors are computed for each frame of the sequence to compute the similarity matrix that distinguishes the largely deviated scans. This involves voxelizing the mesh data and subsequently normalizing it, while also repositioning the center to the mean coordinates of the voxels. The harmonics are computed based on the voxelized mesh data with a voxel resolution R . This involves decomposing the mesh into harmonics by summing and normalizing along the same frequencies. The resulting descriptor captures the information of the shape that is normalized to orientation, translation and scale. The spherical harmonics descriptors, denoted as D , have a shape of (n, d) , where n represents the number of frames in the sequence and d represents the dimensionality of the descriptors. The similarity matrix S is computed as $D \cdot D^T$. The resulting similarity matrix S captures the pairwise similarities between frames in the VV sequence, with S_{ij} representing the similarity between frame i and frame j . In contrast to previous approaches outlined in [16], the method for identifying keyframes involves selecting frames exhibiting the lowest similarity across the mean of rows within the matrix. Additionally, a minimum distance of 5 frames between selected keyframes is enforced to ensure temporal diversity and relevance.

3.2 Pose registration

Registering a human mesh involves integrating a skeletal framework into the model, establishing a hierarchical arrangement of bones or joints corresponding to different body segments. This method entails defining the allowable movement of each bone concerning its parent bone, typically incorporating restrictions and limitations for natural articulation. SMPL is a classical parametric human body template that consists of 24 joints out of which 23 are body joints and one root joint. SMPLH extended SMPL with the addition of a hand model with a total of 52 joints [20]. This models a function $M(\beta, \theta, t)$ that takes shape space vectors (β), pose for each joint (θ), and the global translation (T). The problem of 3D pose registration is to estimate the shape, pose, and translation

Figure 1: Proposed methodology of volumetric video annotation pipeline.

parameters with respect to a canonical shape. To this end, an implicit part network [2], an off-the-shelf tool, is used to register any human scan to an SMPLH model. As the shape parameters (β) are trivial in training the action classifier, only pose parameters (θ) in axis-angle representations relative to root joints are used.

3.3 Semantic annotation

Annotating the textual descriptions to a VV sequence is performed at two levels: First, a textual description of the pose per keyframe is captured using the rule-based description generation [3]. Given the registered pose parameters, the high-level descriptions are derived from 3D key points based on angles, distances, relative positions, and ground contacts. This high-level description is further processed by removing redundant information and aggregating it to convert it into a natural language description. For instance, "Their right forearm is parallel to the ground with their right hand raised over their neck". Second, an action classifier classifies the action of the sequence.

The problem of action classification is formulated as a sentence classification task. Given the pose information of the registered scan $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{72}$, a trained pose encoder that aligns the textual description with posture is used to derive a 512-dimension descriptor (D_{512}). This description in analogy to a natural language sentence classifier is a word token encompassing the information. The information on data preparation and training is specified in Section 4.1.1. Due to the long-tailed distribution of the dataset, the focal loss is used to tackle the class imbalance problem. The architecture of the transformer encoder resembles $BERT_{base}$ with 12 layers, 768 hidden dimensions, and 12 self-attention heads. The positional encoding of sines and cosines is added to the pose-tokens similar to any text classification with transformer task to maintain temporal action consistency.

4 EXPERIMENTS

4.1 Semantic action classification

The annotation pipeline can be leveraged for multiple tasks including keyframe extraction, pose registration, per-frame textual description, and action classification. In this section, the action classification of a volumetric video using a transformer encoder with postures as the tokens is demonstrated. Given a sequence of human motion (x_1, \dots, x_t) the goal is to predict a category Y . The transformer-based action classifier is implemented using PyTorch and trained using a single V100 GPU. The network is trained for 60 epochs with Adam optimizer and a learning rate starting from 10^{-5} decaying by 0.1 every 15 epochs.

4.1.1 Dataset. The transformer-based action classifier is trained using the AMASS motion-captured dataset. For the task of action classification, the network focally considers only the rotational information of joints in SMPLH format, and other shape parameters are discarded. The BABEL dataset is used to supplement the action labels for training. Segments of actions that are associated with only one class label without simultaneous actions are used for training and testing the action classifier. Segments less than 1 second are not considered for training or testing. A random set of 64 frames are selected in a sequence to feed the transformer encoder as a sentence classification task for training and testing. The rationale behind choosing random samples instead of extracted keyframes from the sequence to train the action classifier is due to the current limited availability of long VV's for testing purposes. Currently, longer VV's are captured for proprietary or production purposes and are not necessarily open-sourced. The proposed solution appears constrained unless longer VV's become more widely available. Additionally, it is observed that actions like *laugh* encode little to no information for classifying an action. This can be observed from the comparison of the pairwise cosine similarity matrix of the sequences as illustrated in Figure 2.

The motivation for rejecting classes that have significantly lesser cosine similarity is to avoid any bias toward the classes that can not

Figure 2: Similarity matrices for *laugh* and *move* actions.

encode information in the body model during training. Finally, the classes that exhibit variations in motions are filtered for training resulting in a total of 50 unique action classes resulting in 5200 and 1300, training and testing segments, respectively. The joint positions of SMPLH model is normalized using the standard model as mentioned in [3].

4.1.2 Action classification. The top-k metrics provide insights into the percentage of true classes present among the top-k scoring predictions. Top-1 and top-5 accuracy metrics are used to evaluate the performance of the transformer-based action classifier. The performance of the classification model was evaluated using two different loss functions: Focal Loss and Cross-Entropy. The results revealed significant differences in the classification model effectiveness between these two approaches. When trained with Focal Loss, the model achieved top-1 and top-5 classification accuracies of 64.81% and 86.45%, respectively. This indicates the ability of Focal Loss to handle class imbalance problems. In contrast, the utilization of cross entropy led to lower accuracies, with top-1 and top-5 rates reaching only 43.50% and 79.09%, respectively. Due to the long-tailed distribution nature of the dataset, potential bias towards certain classes is observed during training. This is mainly due to inefficient learning due to the class-imbalance problem. The top-1 benchmark for action recognition tasks using GCN [22] stands at 87% on carefully controlled and class-balanced NTU+RGB data [14]. Evaluating the proposed method alongside other approaches presents significant challenges. Firstly, the data prepared for training and testing focuses solely on individual action sequences rather than composed actions, as outlined in the BABEL dataset [19]. Secondly, while action recognition has been extensively studied, temporal segmentation on skeletal data remains relatively unexplored. To the best of our knowledge, succeeding works from BABEL aim to solve the problem of temporal action localization on skeletal data [5, 24, 25]. Evaluating these methods is challenging due to the availability of temporal action skeletal datasets and is done using visual-based methods in skeletal settings using pseudo-labels [9, 26]. These factors collectively hinder comprehensive comparative analysis and highlight the need for further research in this area. The top 10 classes with accurate predictions out of 50 classes are too distant from one another as plotted in Figure 3.

For instance, *cartwheel* and *crawl* involve distinguishing movements from different body parts. However, the annotations labels with only single actions in the BABEL dataset correspond to other sparse actions. For example, *clap* may share high resemblances with *hand movements*, and *touching body parts*. We frequently observe

Figure 3: Top 10 accurate classes predicted by action classifier.

this type of misclassification given the annotations on testing data. However, the model predicts an action class that is of some relevance in the sequence. These insights provide motivation for more precise analysis of temporal action decomposition and decoupling of the motions across different body parts in future works.

4.2 Auto-summarization pipeline

For the task of metadata extraction, a publicly available VV dataset is used to demonstrate the usage of the summarization pipeline [17]. The dataset contains three volumetric sequences of dancing, playing football, and gestures. The volumetric videos in the dataset are captured with multi-camera setup in a controlled environment and contains human action sequences of subjects performing different actions. These sequences are further processed by solving the manifoldness, and excluding the small noise clusters near the surface of the meshes. The resolution of the voxel grid R is set to 32 to extract keyframes using spherical harmonic descriptors. The pose of any arbitrary scan is registered to the neutral body model using [2]. The sub-components of the pipeline use the mesh data of the sequence as the standard inputs except for the semantic action classifier. One primary challenge observed in the annotation pipeline is the inherited errors from the pre-trained networks of pose registration due to relatively loose clothing. The illustration of extracted keyframes with the top-3 predictions of the action classifier is presented in Figure 4.

The top-3 prediction labels for the remaining two sequences of playing football and hand gestures are hand movements, interaction with an object, moving something and looking, spin, head movements, respectively. The action classifier trained on poses as word tokens from the BABEL dataset, not only demonstrates the advantages of addressing the action classification as a language model but also the generalizability of the model on new data. Finally, the metadata extracted from the proposed pipeline encapsulates key information of the sequence including keyframes, rigged pose information, posecodes per keyframes, and semantic action labels. This metadata could be used in tackling major downstream tasks such as motion interpolation between keyframes, searching a pose from posecodes in the sequence, and searching a VV sequence from a collection.

Figure 4: Keyframes extracted with top 3 predicted labels.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this paper introduces an automatic summarization pipeline for human volumetric videos. Additionally, the proposed approach to classifying human actions through pose-based word token representations in language models presents a novel methodology. The metadata extracted through this pipeline supplements across a spectrum of downstream tasks. While this paper opens new avenues for research, future endeavors will focus on addressing challenges such as disambiguating actions in scenarios involving simultaneous actions from different body parts. These endeavors promise to enhance the accuracy and robustness of action classification, thereby contributing to the advancement of human activity recognition.

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